

**Mummified Fruit as a Source of Inoculum and Disease Dynamics of Olive
Anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* spp.**

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ABSTRACT

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Anthracnose, caused by *Colletotrichum* spp., is a destructive disease of olive fruit worldwide. Management of this disease requires information on the influence of weather on inoculum production and information on the dynamics of fruit infection on olive cultivars that differ in resistance. The pathogen produced very large numbers of conidia on rotted ($>1.87 \times 10^8$ conidia per fruit) or mummified ($>2 \times 10^4$ conidia per fruit) olive fruit, but conidial production was highly influenced by agronomical and weather factors. Conidial production on mummified fruit was for susceptible cultivars incubated at 20 to 25°C and increased with increasing wetness duration up to 96 h. Repeated washings of mummified fruit reduced conidial production, which was very low after five washings. Mummified fruit, which are the main source of inoculum for anthracnose epidemics, produced many more conidia when placed in the tree canopy than on or in the soil. Anthracnose epidemics on susceptible cultivars Hojiblanca and Picudo during three seasons (2005–2008) were determined by rainfall, temperature, and

fruit ripening, and had three main phases: the latent period (May–October), during which latent infections in September and October; the onset of the epidemic, which coincided with the beginning of fruit ripening (early November); and disease development, which was predicted by the Weibull model (November–March). No epidemics developed on the susceptible cultivars during the driest season (2007/2008) or on the resistant cultivar Picual during any of the three seasons.

Anthracnose is the most important disease of olive (*Olea europaea* L.) fruit throughout the world, particularly in the humid areas where susceptible cultivars are grown, such as Portugal or the Catalonia and the Andalusia regions of Spain (16,21,28). Andalusia (southern Spain) is the largest olive-growing region in the world (> 1.5 million ha), and in some provinces, such as Jaén, all of the land used for agriculture is planted with olive (2).

Olive anthracnose is caused by the fungal pathogens *Colletotrichum acutatum* J. H. Simmonds and *C. gloeosporioides* (Penz.) Penz. & Sacc. (15). Based on DNA sequences of the ITS rDNA and β -tubulin gene regions, however, *C. acutatum* has been recently subdivided into *C. acutatum*, *C. fiorinae*, and *C. simmondsii* (27), with *C. acutatum* and *C. simmondsii* being the dominant species in the central Andalusian region and Portugal (20).

In Andalusia, the life cycle of *C. acutatum* on olive has been recently elucidated. Infection occurs at all stages of fruit development, from flower bud emergence to ripening. After infection of the developing fruit, the fungus enters a latent period from which it emerges during fruit ripening in the autumn–early winter season, causing fruit rot and the production of abundant conidia (21). During this season, conidia can be rain-splashed to other fruit and cause secondary infections before the fruit is harvested in late

autumn or early winter; thus, the disease is oligocyclic. When the temperature rises and the relative humidity decreases, rotten fruit are mummified (31). A toxin produced by the pathogen in the infected fruit causes leaf wilting and branch dieback symptoms. Although the pathogen infects the leaves and shoots of olive, fungal conidiomata (acervuli) or conidial masses do not develop on these tissues in Andalusia (21) unless the infected tissues are incubated in humid chambers for > 1 month (20). Mummified fruit are the most important inoculum source for the disease. Mateo-Sagasta (17) indicated that the fungus might survive in mummies on the soil surface. Other authors, however, found that the fungus survives as mummies in the olive canopy because mummies on the soil surface are buried by soil cultivation or destroyed by insects and secondary invaders (6,28). The effects of environmental conditions and the susceptibility of olive cultivars on inoculum production by infected or mummified fruit are unclear. In addition, estimation of the possible risk of fruit infection should be based on an understanding of seasonal patterns of inoculum production on mummified fruit and of factors affecting fruit infection. In other countries, such as Greece, Italy, and Australia, infected leaves are a secondary inoculum source because the pathogen sometimes develops acervuli in these tissues (13,14,26,35).

Quantitative comparisons of plant epidemics help researchers evaluate the effects of various disease management strategies and tactics on disease dynamics (11). The progress of olive anthracnose epidemics is influenced by several factors, including weather conditions (9,20,28,30), cultivar susceptibility (17,18,20), and fruit maturity (17,19). Nevertheless, most of these studies have been carried out under controlled or field conditions very different from those in the Mediterranean basin (9). Research is needed on the biology and dynamics of anthracnose epidemics in the Mediterranean

region because this region is the world's largest producer of olives and is the center of olive diversity (3).

In this study, laboratory and field experiments were conducted to obtain the information required for a decision support system for the management of olive anthracnose. One objective of this study was to quantify conidial production from rotted and mummified fruit as affected by temperature, wetness duration, and other factors in the Mediterranean region. A second objective was to determine the effects of cultivar resistance and fruit ripeness on the development of epidemics studied during three seasons. A preliminary report has been published (22).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Production of soapy fruit and mummified fruit. Ripe olive fruit were collected from healthy field-grown trees in the province of Córdoba (southern Spain). Fruit of the following three widely grown olive cultivars with different degrees of resistance to anthracnose were used: Hojiblanca (highly susceptible), Picual (resistant), and Picudo (highly susceptible) (18). Fruit were washed, disinfested, air-dried, and sprayed with a conidial suspension (10^5 conidia per ml) as previously reported (19). Inoculations were performed with isolate Col-87 of *C. acutatum*-group A4; this group, which was classified according to its internal transcribed spacer 5.8S and β -tubulin regions (29), is the pathogenically dominant group in central Andalusia (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*). Inoculated fruit were incubated in humidity chambers (plastic containers, $22 \times 16 \times 10$ cm³, with 100% RH) at 23 ± 2 °C under fluorescent lights (12 h photoperiod, $350 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). Olive fruit that became completely rotted and that produced abundant conidia in a gelatinous matrix (i.e., "soapy fruit") were removed from the humidity chambers 1 month after inoculation for use in experiments. The

soapy fruit were incubated in the same plastic containers on natural soil for an additional 21 days to produce mummified fruit.

Quantification of conidial production from soapy fruit and mummies. For quantification of conidial production in the experiments described later in this paper, soapy fruit or mummies were placed in 1.0- or 0.5-liter Erlenmeyer flasks with 100, 300, or 500 ml of sterile water with 1.5 ml of Tween® 20 per liter and a magnetic stir-bar depending on the experiment. For removal of conidia from infected fruit, flasks were placed successively in an ultrasonic bath (Selecta, Barcelona, Spain) for 5 min and in a magnetic agitator for 5 min. The inoculum density of *C. acutatum* was measured with a hemacytometer, and the total number of conidia was calculated according to the volume of water. With this information (and data for fruit surface area), the conidial production per surface area of fruit was calculated. The area of each fruit was calculated as the area of a sphere (πd^2) whose diameter was the mean of two perpendicular diameters. Viability of the conidia, as determined by assessment of germination in the flasks or on acidified potato dextrose agar (PDA) plus copper sulphate (21), was always greater than 85%.

Effect of cultivar on conidial production from soapy fruit. Conidial production from soapy fruit of cvs. Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo was determined as described in the previous section. The experiment was arranged in a completely randomized design with five replicates of 10 fruit per cultivar. The experiment was conducted twice, and the data presented are the average of two experiments (error variances were homogeneous, and there were no significant differences between the experiments). Data were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis one-way nonparametric test, and means were compared at $P = 0.05$. Data from this experiment and other experiments were analyzed with SPSS (version 14; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL) except as noted.

Effect of temperature on conidial production from mummified fruit. Mummified fruit of cv. Hojiblanca were incubated in humid chambers in continuous dark at 5°C intervals from 5 to 35°C, and conidial production was measured after 72 h. Each temperature was represented by three replicate humid chambers (20 mummified fruit per chamber). The experiment was conducted twice, and the data from both experiments were averaged because a least significant difference (LSD) test did not detect significant differences between experiments at any temperature. Conidial production at temperature T ($Y_{(T)}$) was estimated from a temperature response function ($f_{(T)}$) and a maximum value (CP_{max}) of conidial production, which are analogous to the response function and maximum value of disease severity previously used to describe the effect of wetness duration on infection (12).

$$Y_{(T)} = f_{(T)} \times CP_{max} \quad (1)$$

The temperature function ($f_{(T)}$) uses the pathogen's cardinal temperatures to estimate the shape parameter and temperature response (34):

$$f_{(T)} = \left(\frac{T_{max} - T}{T_{max} - T_{opt}} \right) \left(\frac{T - T_{min}}{T_{opt} - T_{min}} \right)^{\left(\frac{T_{opt} - T_{min}}{T_{max} - T_{opt}} \right)} \quad (2)$$

where T = mean temperature (°C) during the incubation period, T_{min} = minimum temperature for sporulation, T_{max} = maximum temperature for sporulation, and T_{opt} = optimum temperature for sporulation. The observed data from the experiments were compared with model predictions of $Y_{(T)}$ based on the coefficient of determination (R^2), coefficient of determination adjusted for degrees of freedom (R_a^2), the root mean square error (RMS), and the pattern of residuals (11). Magarey's model was selected after consideration of other models, such as the Analytis Beta function and the Schödter angular model (7).

Effect of wetness period on conidial production on mummified fruit. The effect of wetness period on conidial production on mummified fruit was studied using mummies of cv. Hojiblanca that were incubated in humid chambers in the dark for 0, 12, 24, 48, 72, 96, or 168 h at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. After these incubations, conidial production on mummified fruit was assessed as described above. Each wetness period was represented by five humid chambers (20 mummies per chamber). The experiment was conducted twice, and the data from both experiments were averaged. Linear regression was used to evaluate the relationships between the length of the wetness period and conidial production.

Effect of repeated washings on conidial production from mummified fruit. Mummies of cv. Hojiblanca were subjected to successive incubation–washing treatments to determine the effect of repeated rainfall events on conidial production. The mummies were incubated in humid chambers in the dark for 96 h at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and conidial production was assessed as described above. The same mummified fruit were then dried at room temperature for 1 week before they were hydrated in humid chambers for 96 h under the same conditions, and conidial production was assessed again. The same process was repeated 14 times. Five humid chambers (20 mummified fruit per chamber) were used. The test was conducted twice, and the data from both tests were averaged. Nonlinear regression was used to study the relationship between accumulated conidial production and the number of washing treatments. Goodness of fit was evaluated using R^2 , R_a^2 , the pattern of residuals, and the number of iterations required by the Marquardt algorithm to converge on the parameter estimated.

Conidial production on mummified fruit that were placed in the tree canopy, placed on the soil surface, or buried in the soil. This experiment was conducted in an cv. Picual olive orchard located near Córdoba city. At the beginning of May 2006 and

2008, mummies were placed inside nylon mesh bags (10 mummies per bag). Each year, 90 nylon bags were placed in the olive canopy, placed on the soil surface under the tree canopy, or buried in the soil at 5 cm depth under the tree canopy (10 bags per each of five repeated trees and location). One nylon bag from each location and tree were collected monthly, and conidial production in humid chambers was assessed as described earlier. Conidial production (mean and standard error of means) was calculated monthly for each year.

Dynamics of fruit infection in the field. Eighteen olive trees (six each of cvs. Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo) were selected to study the effects of cultivar resistance and fruit ripeness on the development of anthracnose epidemics. The three cultivars were planted in an agronomical trial in 1987 with a 7×7 m spacing and with one trunk per tree. The trees were located in the 'La Mina' orchard of the Andalusian Institute for Research and Formation in Agriculture and Fishery (IFAPA in Spanish) Center in Cabra, Córdoba Province (37.28 N, 4.26 W). The climate is typical of the Mediterranean region with a mean annual precipitation of 702 mm and a marked summer drought (< 30 mm of rain from June through September). The experimental orchard was managed according to the practices used in commercial olive orchards in Andalusia (2). At the beginning of October of each year, between 420 and 460 fruit (~110 fruit per cardinal direction) were randomly marked in the canopy of each tree. The fruit were periodically accessed from November to March for anthracnose symptoms (with or without) and ripeness [color class from 0 (green fruit) to 4 (black fruit);1]. In addition, 1100 to 1500 asymptomatic fruit of each cultivar were randomly collected, and the percentage of fruit with latent infections of *C. acutatum* was periodically determined using the herbicide N,N'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium dichloride (Paraquat) (21). The number of fallen fruit with and without symptoms was assessed

from a total of 4 m² of soil surface per tree (1 m² per cardinal direction) that was marked using four 1-m² wooden frames for each tree. The numbers of symptomatic and asymptomatic fruit on the soil surface were counted periodically, and the fruit were removed from the frames after each count. The study was carried out during three agronomical seasons: 2005/06, 06/07, and 07/08. In each season, six new olive trees per cultivar were selected in the same agronomical trial. The accumulated proportion of symptomatic fruit in the canopy plus on the soil was calculated for each replicate tree using the following formula:

$$I = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=0}^{t=n} Sct + (Dt \times Sst) \quad (3)$$

where I is the accumulated proportion per tree at t th observation, Sct is the number of symptomatic fruit in the olive canopy at t th observation, Dt is the fallen fruit at t th observation, Sst is the proportion (0-1) of symptomatic fruit on the soil surface at t th observation, n is the total number of observations, and N is the number of marked fruit (~ 440). The disease progress curves (DPCs) were obtained for the proportion of affected fruit over time in days from the date of appearance of the first affected fruit in the experimental trial around the first week of November. The nonlinear form of the Weibull model was evaluated for goodness-of-fit to the set of I progress data using nonlinear regression analysis with the Marquardt algorithm as described above. The Weibull model is a generalized, simple model that includes both rate and shape parameters, which allows it to generate a wide variety of response curves according to the equation:

$$Y = A(1 - \exp\{-[B(t - C)]^p\}) \quad (4)$$

where Y = accumulated incidence index (0-1), A = upper asymptote parameter (i.e., upper limit of Y), B = scale parameter (i.e., intrinsic rate of Y increase over time), C =

location parameter (i.e., length of delay before the onset of the epidemic development), D = shape parameter (i.e., location of inflection point), and t = time of disease assessment in days after the first of November (24). The area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) was calculated by trapezoidal integration of I values over time for each replication. Finally, linear regression was used to evaluate fruit ripening (Fr) over time (t) according to $Fr = a \times bt$, where b = ripening rate (day^{-1}). Fruit ripening was evaluated from the first week of November of each year until the fruit were completely ripe (i.e., black). The effect of cultivar on the dependent variables was separately studied for each season because of important differences between weather conditions among years. Dependent variables [parameters of the Weibull model (A , B , C , and D), final incidence, and AUDPC] were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), and means were compared with the Fisher's protected Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at $P = 0.05$. For assessment of the effect of the cardinal position of fruit on the tree, ANOVA was performed using each tree as a block. The relationship between ripening rate (b) of each olive tree and all dependent variables was studied using Pearson's correlation test. For each cultivar, linear regression was used to evaluate the fruit ripening rate (b) over final incidence, and regression lines of cultivars were compared based on their homogeneity of variances, slopes, and intercepts (Statistix® 9, Analytical Software, Tallahassee, FL).

RESULTS

Effect of cultivar on conidial production from soapy fruit. The pathogen produced very large numbers of conidia on soapy fruit, i.e., from 1.87×10^8 to 1.04×10^9 conidia per fruit. According to the Kruskal-Wallis test, conidial production on soapy fruit differed ($P = 0.0004$) among cultivars. *Colletotrichum acuatum* produced more conidia on the susceptible cv. Picudo than on the resistant cv. Picual. The production of

conidia did not differ ($P > 0.05$) between the susceptible cv. Hojiblanca and the other two cultivars (Fig. 1A). The number of conidia per unit of fruit surface was smaller on the resistant cv. Picual than on the susceptible cvs. Hojiblanca and Picudo ($P = 0.0134$) but did not differ between the susceptible cultivars ($P > 0.05$) (Fig. 1B).

Effect of temperature on conidial production on mummified fruit. Temperature significantly ($P < 0.0001$) influenced conidial production on mummified fruit. Viable conidia were detected at all temperatures studied (Fig. 2). The fewest conidia were produced at 5 and 35°C, and the number was smaller at 35°C than at 5°C. Conidial production increased with increasing temperatures to a maximum near 20°C and decreased between 25 and 35°C. This relationship was well described by equation 1 (Fig. 2), for which the parameters T_{min} , T_{max} , and T_{opt} were established according to the experimental data as 0, 35, and 22°C, respectively. Thus, equation 2 can be rewritten as:

$$f_{(T)} = (2.6923 - T/13) \times (T/22)^{1.6923} . \quad (5)$$

Comparison of the observed data and the data generated by equation 5 indicates that $R^2 = 0.866$, $R_a^2 = 0.839$, and $RMS = 1.248$.

Effect of wetness period on conidial production from mummified fruit. The mummified olive fruit increased substantially in size when they were hydrated in humid chambers at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Wetness period significantly ($P = 0.0032$) affected conidial production of *C. acutatum* on mummified fruit, and conidial production per unit area of fruit surface increased linearly with increasing wetness duration from 0 to 96 h (Fig. 3). The linear trend was significant ($P = 0.0006$), but the quadratic or cubic trends were not significant ($P > 0.05$). The following regression line fit the data well:

$$Y = 2.1592 - 0.0859X$$

in which Y = conidial production ($\times 10^4$) and X = wetness duration (h) (Fig. 3). The slope parameter was significant ($P < 0.0001$); R^2 and R_a^2 were 0.960 and 0.950, respectively. Conversely, there was a substantial reduction in number of conidia per unit area of surface when the wetness duration was 168 h (*data not shown*). After 96 h of incubation, the mummified fruit were heavily colonized by saprophytic fungi, mainly species of *Mucor* and *Rhizopus*, and some bacteria, and these apparently inhibited the production of conidia by *C. acutatum*.

Effect of repeated washings on conidial production from mummified fruit. The cumulative number of viable conidia of *C. acutatum* produced on mummified olive fruit increased markedly with up to five incubation–washing treatments and then increased only slightly, according to the fitted asymptotic model (Fig. 3). According to this model, the asymptote was at about 10^5 conidia per mm^2 of mummified fruit. The asymptotic model that best described the influence of the washing treatment on inoculum production was:

$$Y = -10.1751 - 3.2098 \times 0.5923^X$$

in which Y = cumulative conidial production ($\times 10^4$) and X = number of washing treatments (Fig. 4). All estimated parameters of the equation were significant ($P < 0.05$), and R^2 and R_a^2 were 0.933 and 0.921, respectively.

Conidial production on mummified fruit that were placed in the tree canopy, placed on the soil surface, or buried in the soil. From May to October in 2006 and 2008, the pathogen produced viable conidia on mummified fruit that were placed in all three locations (Fig. 5). Between 10^3 - and 10^4 -times more conidia were produced on mummies in the tree canopy (aerial mummies) than on mummies on the soil surface or buried in the soil. Mummies on or in the soil were rapidly colonized by saprophytic

fungi, mainly species of *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, and *Mucor* (*data not shown*). In both years, the number of conidia per unit surface area of aerial mummy decreased slightly with time but peaked in October 2006 and in September 2008, which coincided with the first rainfall after summer (Fig. 5).

Disease dynamics in the field. In the 3 years of this study, two seasons were favorable for olive anthracnose epidemics (2005/06 and 2006/07) and one season was unfavorable (2007/08). Although spring infection of young fruit was not estimated, the level of latent infection of fruit after hot, dry summers was <1% in the 3 years. However, latent infection of fruit increased from September to October before the onset of epidemics. In this period, rainfall totals were 409, 327, and 244 mm in 2005, 2006, and 2007, respectively. At the onset of epidemics in early November, latent infection of fruit varied greatly among years and cultivars (Table 1). On the susceptible cvs. Hojiblanca and Picudo, severe epidemics developed during the two favorable seasons. The first symptomatic fruit appeared in early November when the fruit changed color from green-yellow to violet. However, some rotted fruit were detected on olive trees adjacent to the experimental orchard at the end of October, although the fruit in these trees were riper than the fruit in the study. After the first affected fruit were detected, disease incidence and latent infection increased markedly until the end of December. Additionally, there was another important increase of disease incidence during March 2007, when the temperature increased (Fig. 6). On the resistant cv. Picual, anthracnose rarely occurred on fruit in the favorable seasons (final incidence of affected fruit <3%, Fig. 6, Table 1), and no disease symptoms were observed during the driest season (2007/08, Table 1). Conversely, the final incidence of affected fruit in the driest season was 12.4% and 0.3% on cvs. Hojiblanca and Picudo, respectively (Table 1). Overall, the

dependent variables were not affected ($P > 0.05$) by the orientation of the branches according to the cardinal directions during the three seasons (*data not shown*).

The increase in the incidence of affected fruit over time was adequately described by the Weibull model ($R^2 > 0.86$) for the susceptible cvs. Picudo and Hojiblanca in the two favorable seasons, but no model satisfactorily described the data for susceptible cultivars in the unfavorable season or for the resistant cultivar Picual in the three seasons because of the low values of disease incidence (Table 1). Although the proportion of symptomatic fruit varied substantially among the six replicated olive trees of each cultivar during both favorable seasons, the effect of cultivar was still significant. The final proportion of affected fruit and AUDPC was generally lower with cv. Picual, although it did not significantly differ ($P > 0.05$) between cv. Picual and cv. Picudo in the season that was unfavorable for disease (Table 1). Of the two susceptible cultivars, Picudo had a significantly ($P < 0.05$) greater final incidence of affected fruit and AUDPC than cv. Hojiblanca in 2005/06. In 2006/07, however, differences between both cultivars were smaller than in the previous season, although the onset of the epidemic (parameter C of the Weibull model) was significantly ($P < 0.05$) delayed by 16.5 days on cv. Hojiblanca relative to cv. Picudo (Table 1). The upper asymptote (A) and accumulated incidence index (Y) of the Weibull model were greater ($P < 0.05$) for cv. Hojiblanca than for cv. Picudo.

The incidence of fruit with latent infection in the olive canopy was generally greater than the incidence of fruit with visible symptoms for all cultivars and seasons, although that difference was especially notable for the resistant cv. Picual (Fig. 6). In the fallen fruit, the percentage of anthracnose-affected fruit was greater than that in the tree canopy for the susceptible cvs. Hojiblanca and Picudo in the two favorable seasons (Fig. 6), but there were no differences in the unfavorable season (2007/08) or for the cv.

Picual in the three years (*data not shown*). Among the three cultivars, the fruit ripening rate [b (day⁻¹)] was lowest for the late-ripening cv. Picudo and highest for the early-ripening cv. Picual, although the rate did not differ between cv. Picual and cv. Hojiblanca in 2006/07 (Table 1). In each susceptible cultivar, the fruit ripening rate of each tree in the three seasons was correlated (Pearson's test; $P < 0.05$) with the final incidence of affected fruit (Fig. 7). Final incidence of affected fruit of the susceptible cvs. Hojiblanca and Picudo, but not of the resistant cv. Picual, increased linearly with the ripening rate of fruit (R^2 and $R_a^2 > 0.600$; $P < 0.001$). The slopes of the regression line was greater ($P = 0.0008$) for cv. Picudo than for cv. Hojiblanca (Fig. 7).

DISCUSSION

Although rotted or mummified fruit have been considered as the main inoculum source for olive anthracnose (6,17,21,30,31), the current study is the first to quantify conidial production on mummified olive fruit. By monitoring symptomatic and non-symptomatic olive fruit during three seasons in the field, the current study also determined disease dynamics and optimal infection periods. In the spring, conidia of the pathogen are dispersed by rain splashing from mummified fruit to developing fruit (pea sized), causing latent infections. In the next autumn, when the fruit are ripening, the pathogen become active, causes fruit rot, and produces large numbers of conidia that initiate secondary disease cycles (21,30,31). At the end of winter, the rotted fruit mummify when the humidity decreases and the temperature increases, and the mummified fruit are then the main source of conidia for infection of developing fruit during the following spring (21,31).

Others authors, however, have reported that infected leaves and shoots are the major inoculum source for anthracnose infection of developing olive fruit (5,28), because the pathogen can develop secondary conidia (28) or form acervuli in these infected tissues

(14,26,35). In a previous study in southern Spain, Moral et al. (21) reported that the pathogen infected the leaves and shoots of olive but did not develop acervuli or conidia masses on these tissues. Artificially infected vegetative tissues only produced conidia when they were incubated at 100% RH for more than 1 month (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*), but these weather conditions are unlikely to occur in the Mediterranean climate where olives are grown. In field experiments in Spain and Portugal, the percentage of non-symptomatic infected leaves decreased from the end of winter until summer, when the percentage of pathogen isolation was very low (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*; 28). Whether or not small numbers of conidia are produced on vegetative tissues, the huge quantity of viable conidia that the fungus produces on mummified fruit (5×10^8 conidia per mummy) suggests that mummies are a much more important inoculum source than leaves and shoots.

Factors influencing conidial production on mummified olive fruit have not been previously reported. In this study, olive cultivar, temperature, and wetness duration greatly influenced conidial production on olive mummies. The optimum temperature range of 20 to 25°C observed for conidial production on mummified fruit was similar to that previously reported for germination of conidia (8,23) and infection of fruit (20). However, Kaul and Thakur (9) reported an optimal temperature between 17 and 22°C for leaf infection in the field. Likewise, the production of conidia increased with wetness duration in the current study, but when the wetness period was longer than 96 h, conidial production was reduced, probably because mummies were colonized by saprophytic microorganisms.

After a moderate or severe epidemic, most mummified fruit fall to the soil surface because the fungus infects the fruit peduncle. Very few mummies (~ 1 mummy per tree) remain in the tree canopy until the next autumn, but this low number of mummies in the

canopy decreased drastically if there was not a new epidemic in the autumn (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*). Mateo-Sagasta (17) indicated that the fungus might survive in mummies on the soil surface, although other authors suggested that the fungus survives as mummies in the olive canopy (6). In our study, the pathogen produced viable conidia on mummies in the canopy and on and in the soil throughout the year, but produced 10^3 - to 10^4 -times more conidia on aerial mummies than on those that were buried in the soil or placed on the soil surface. Mummies in or on the soil were colonized by saprophytic microorganisms, and this probably explains the drastic reduction in number of conidia on the mummies in contact with the soil. A similar reduction in conidial numbers on mummies that were buried or on the soil surface has been reported (6,35). Recently, Talhinhos *et al.* (28) reported that the fungus could not be isolated from mummified fruit collected from the soil surface. The latter authors, however, checked for the presence of the pathogen in mummies by isolating on potato dextrose agar (PDA) rather than by washing the mummies as was done in our study.

The study of disease dynamics during the autumn–winter period showed that the incidence of fruit with latent or visible infections was highly affected by olive cultivar, weather conditions, and fruit ripeness. Thus, there were no epidemics in the resistant cultivar in any season and only minor epidemic development on the susceptible cultivars during the driest season (2007/08). Several authors reported a positive correlation between rainfall during the autumn–winter and disease severity, although this information was based on field observation rather than on systematic study (9,15,17,28,35). Data from our study confirmed that rainfall is an essential factor for olive anthracnose development in susceptible cultivars because it determined the level of latent infection of fruit before the onset of the epidemics (September–October) and the further progress of the epidemics. Moreover, the pathogen presumably can produce

large numbers of conidia even after several rainfall periods that were simulated in this study with the washing treatments of mummies.

Like rainfall, temperature influenced the development of anthracnose epidemics on the susceptible cultivars. After the first affected fruit were detected at the beginning of November, incidence of latent-infected and affected fruit increased until the middle of December when the mean temperature decreased to around 7°C. Overall, at this time, there were more fruit with latent infections than with symptoms. After that, the proportion of symptomatic fruit increased slowly but most infection remained latent until February–March when temperature increased again. Other authors have observed that the latent period of the disease is substantially lengthened when the fruit are incubated at low temperatures (10,20).

Fruit susceptibility to anthracnose increases with ripeness (17,19), and fruit ripening was the key factor determining the onset of epidemics on susceptible cultivars in the current study. Moreover, the first anthracnose-affected fruit did not appear until the beginning of November when fruit changed from green-yellow to violet [ripening stage 2 (1)]. The onset and rate of fruit ripening, in addition to being affected by temperature and photoperiod, is also influenced by the fruit load on trees, i.e., fruit ripen faster on trees with a lower fruit load (2). Because the fruit load on trees depends on the previous year's harvest, the yield-reducing factors in a given year, such as anthracnose, increase the onset and rate of ripening in the next year. If ripening occurs earlier and faster in a susceptible cultivar, the fruit of that cultivar will be available for the development of anthracnose epidemics earlier in fall, when temperature and rain and increased inoculum produced by the previous year's epidemic favor epidemics in the current year. As a consequence, the occurrence of an anthracnose epidemic in one year increases the

probability of an epidemic in the next year. Episodes of concatenated epidemics are well known for olive anthracnose (15,17,30,31).

In this study, the onset and disease development rate of epidemics varied among trees of each susceptible cultivar. These differences among trees of the same cultivar in the same field are common in olive orchards (18,19), and they appear to be related to differences in the rate of fruit ripening of each tree (as affected by the fruit load) and to differences in the quantity of available inoculum from the previous year.

The onset and duration of fruit ripening also varies with the cultivar (2), although cultivar susceptibility is not related with the time of fruit ripeness (18). In our study, the ripening rate varied greatly among cultivars and was highest with cv. Picual and lowest with cv. Picudo. In this case, the early fruit ripening of Picual, which should favor anthracnose disease, was balanced by the genetic resistance of this cultivar. As noted in the previous paragraph, the fruit ripening rate for each olive tree of the susceptible cultivars was positively correlated with the final incidence of affected fruit, so that differences in disease incidence among olive trees of the same cultivar were evidently related to their ripening rate. Although cvs. Hojiblanca and Picudo are highly susceptible to anthracnose, cv. Picudo is slightly more susceptible than cv. Hojiblanca under field conditions because the pathogen can produce symptoms on green fruit of cv. Picudo but it cannot do so on green fruit of cv. Hojiblanca (18). This difference in susceptibility influenced the anthracnose in 2006/07. Thus, the onset of the epidemic (parameter C of Weibull's model) was about 15 days later in cv. Hojiblanca than in cv. Picudo. Because of the importance of this delay factor, the planting of late-ripening susceptible cultivars has been recommended as a control measure if resistant cultivars are not available (4,19). Also, growers could take advantage of this delay by harvesting early, which is an important practice for controlling the disease (19,30,31).

In the present study, the incidence of affected fruit of the resistant cv. Picual was nil or very low (<2.5%), even when environmental conditions were favorable for disease development and inoculum from the previous year was abundant in the orchard. In olive orchards where only resistant cultivars are planted, treatments with copper-based fungicides during the autumn are not needed to control anthracnose, but they are frequently done in olive growing areas, such as in Jaén province, where the resistant cv. Picual is the dominant cultivar (25,30,31). In these areas, the application of fungicide in late winter–early spring and adequate cultural practices are sufficient to control peacock spot and cercosporiose caused by *Fusicladium oleagineum* and *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, respectively, which are the main foliar diseases (30,33).

The effects of wetness duration and temperature on conidial production from mummified fruit and on development of anthracnose in the field and under controlled conditions have been determined in the current study and in previous studies (18,19,20). This information will facilitate the design of a forecasting system that could be used to determine the timing of fungicide sprays and to develop more efficient management strategies. The use of fungicides should be integrated with the exploitation of cultivar resistance, the early harvesting of fruit or the use of cultivars that ripen more slowly, and the elimination of mummified fruit in the olive canopy. These latter methods of anthracnose control should reduce the need for of fungicides in olive orchards, which cost olive growers in Spain is over \$250 million per year (32).

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LITERATURE CITED

1. Barranco, D., and Rallo, L. 2005. Épocas de floración y maduración. Pages 283-292 in: Variedades de olivo en España. L., Rallo, D., Barranco, J: M., Caballero, C., Del Rio, C., A., Martín, J., Tous, and I., Trujillo, eds. Junta de Andalucía-Consejería de Agricultura y Pesca. Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación y Mundi-Prensa, Madrid, Spain.
2. Barranco, D., Fernández-Escobar, R., and Rallo, L. 2010. Olive growing. Junta de Andalucía / Mundi-Prensa / RIRDC / AOA, Pendle Hill, Australia.
3. Bartolini, G., Petruccelli, R., Tindall, H.D., and Menini, U.G. 2002. Classification, origin, diffusion and history of the olive. FAO, Roma, Italy.
4. Bompeix, G., Julio, E. V. R., and Phillips, D. H. 1988. *Glomerella cingulata* (Stoneman) Spaulding et v. Schrenk. Pages 373-376 in: Manual de enfermedades de las plantas. I. M. Smith, J. Dunez, R. A. Lelliot, D. H. Phillips, and S. A. Archer, eds. Mundi-prensa, Madrid, Spain.
5. Cacciola, S. O., Pane, A., Agosteo, G. E., and Magnano di San Lio, G. 1996. Osservazioni sull' epidemiologia dell'antracnosi dell'olivo in Calabria. Inf. Fitopatol. 6:27-32.
6. Graniti, A., Frisullo, S., Pennisi, A.M., and Magnano di San Lio, G. 1993. Infections of *Glomerella cingulata* on olive in Italy. EPPO Bulletin 23:457-465.

7. Hau, B., and Kranz, J. 1990. Mathematics and statistics for analyses in epidemiology. Pages 15-22 in: Epidemics of Plant Diseases. J. Kranz, ed. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany.
8. Jurado-Bello, J. 2010. Efecto de la temperatura, tiempo de humectación y potencial osmótico en la infección de aceitunas, germinación de conidios y crecimiento micelial de *Colletotrichum* spp. agente causal de la Antracnosis del olivo. Trabajo Profesional Fin de Carrera, ETSIAM, Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba, Spain.
9. Kaul, J. L., and Thakur, R. S. 1985. Incidence of olive anthracnose (*Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* Penz.) and its correlation with weather conditions. J. Tree. Sci. 4:20-34.
10. Loprieno, N., and Tenerini, I. 1960. Indagini sul *Gloeosporium olivarum* Alm., agente della “lebbra” delle olive. Phytopath. Z. 39: 262-290.
11. Madden, L. V., and Campbell, C. L. 1990. Nonlinear disease progress curves. Pages 181-229 in: Epidemics of Plant Diseases, Mathematical Analysis and Modeling, 2nd ed. Ecological Studies 13. J. Kranz, ed. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
12. Magarey, R. D., Sutton, T. B., and Thayer, C. L. 2005. A simple generic infection model for foliar fungal plant pathogens. Phytopathology 95:92-100.
13. Martelli G. P. 1960. Primo contributo alla conoscenza della biologia di *Gloeosporium olivarum* Alm. Phytopath. Medit. 1:31-43.
14. Martelli, G. P. 1961. Acervuli of *Gloeosporium olivarum* on olive leaves. Phytopath. Medit. 1:125-128.
15. Martelli, G. P., and Piglionica, V. 1961. Three year trials against olive ‘leprosi’ in Apulia. Phytopath. Medit. 1:101-112.

16. Martín, M. P., and García-Figueres, F. 1999. *Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* cause anthracnose on olives. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 105:733-741.
17. Mateo-Sagasta, E. 1968. Estudios básicos sobre *Gloeosporium olivarum* Alm. (Deuteromiceto Melanconial). *Bol. Patol. Veg. Entomol. Agric.* 30:31-135.
18. Moral, J., and Trapero, A. 2009. Assessing the susceptibility of olive cultivars to anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Plant Dis.* 93:1028-1036.
19. Moral, J., Bouhmidi, K., and Trapero, A. 2008. Influence of fruit maturity, cultivar susceptibility, and inoculation method on infection of olive fruit by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Plant Dis.* 92:1421-1426.
20. Moral, J., Jurado-Bello, J., Sánchez, M. I., Oliveira, R., and Trapero, A. 2011. Effect of temperature, wetness duration, and planting density on olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. *Phytopathology* 101: (in revision).
21. Moral, J., Oliveira, R., and Trapero, A. 2009. Elucidation of the disease cycle of olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Phytopathology* 99:548-556.
22. Moral, J., Vicente, M., and Trapero, A. 2010. Infected fruit as source of inoculum and infection dynamic on olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Phytopathology* 100: S87-S88.
23. Oliveira, R., Moral, J., Bouhmidi, K., and Trapero, A. 2005. Caracterización morfológica y cultural de aislados de *Colletotrichum* spp. causantes de la Antracnosis del olivo. *Bol. San. Veg. Plagas* 31:531-548.
24. Pennypacker, S. P., Knoble, H. D., Antle, C. E., and Madden, L. V. 1980. A flexible model for studying plant disease progression. *Phytopathology* 70:232-235.

25. Roca, L. F., Moral, J., Viruega, J. R., Ávila, A., Oliveira, R., and Trapero, A. 2007. Copper fungicides in the control of olive diseases. *Olea* 26:48-50.
26. Sergeeva, V., Spooner-Hart, R., and Nair, N. G. 2008. First report of *Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* causing leaf spots of olives (*Olea europaea*) in Australia. *Australasian Plant Dis. Notes* 3:143–144
27. Shivas, R. G., and Tan, Y. P. 2009. A taxonomic re-assessment of *Colletotrichum acutatum*, introducing *C. fiorinae* comb. et stat. nov. and *C. simmondsii* sp. nov. *Fungal Diversity* 39: 111-122.
28. Talhinhos, P., Mota-Capitão, C., Martins, S., Ramos, A. P., Neves-Martins, J., Guerra-Guimarães, L., Várzea, V., Silva, M. C., Sreenivasaprasad, S., and Oliveira, H. 2011. Epidemiology, histopathology and aetiology of olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* in Portugal. *Plant Pathology* 60:483-495.
29. Talhinhos, P., Sreenivasaprasad, S., Neves-Martins, J., and Oliveira, H. 2005. Molecular and phenotypic analyses reveal association of diverse *Colletotrichum acutatum* groups and a low level of *C. gloeosporioides* with olive anthracnose. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 71:2987-2998.
30. Trapero, A., and Blanco, M. A. 2010. Diseases. Pages 521-578 in: *Olive growing*. D. Barranco, R. Fernández-Escobar, and L. Rallo, eds. Junta de Andalucía / Mundi-Prensa / RICD / AOA, Pendle Hill, Australia.
31. Trapero, A., and Moral, J. 2008. Anthracnose of olive caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. Pages 27-28 in: *Colletotrichum Diseases of Fruit Crops*. N. Peres, and P. Timmer, eds. International Congress of Plant Pathology, Torino, Italy.

32. Trapero, A., Roca, L.F., and Moral, J. 2009. Perspectivas futuras del control químico de las enfermedades del olivo. *Phytoma España* 212:80-82.
33. Viruega, J. R., Roca, L. F., Moral, J., and Trapero, A. 2011. Factors affecting infection and disease development on olive leaves inoculated with *Fusicladium oleagineum*. *Plant Dis.* 95:1139-1146.
34. Yin, X., Kropff, M. J., McLaren, G., and Visperas, R. M. 1995. A nonlinear model for crop development as a function of temperature. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 77:1-16.
35. Zachos, D. G., and Makris, S. A. 1963. Studies on *Gloeosporium olivarum* in Greece II: Symptoms of the disease. *Annales Institut Phytopathologique Benaki* 5:128-130.

TABLE 1. Weibull's model parameters, final incidence (proportion of symptomatic fruit), and area under disease progress curve for anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* on the olive cultivars Hojiblanca (susceptible), Picudo (susceptible), and Picual (resistant) in southern Spain^a

Season (autumn mm) ^c	rainfall, (mm)	Weibull's model parameters ^b					Final Incidence (0-1)	Latent infection ^d (%)	AUDPC ^e	Slope ^f (= <i>b</i>)	<i>R</i> ^{2f}
		A	B	C	D	Y					
2005/2006	(409.2)										
Picudo		0.443a	0.252a	8.791a	2.662a	0.405a	0.405a	23.5	34.40a	0.011c	0.888
Hojiblanca		0.199b	0.172a	4.511a	2.272a	0.183b	0.184b	14.4	12.89b	0.040b	0.891
Picual		-	-	-	-	-	0.018c	19.1	0.270c	0.054a	0.816
2006/2007	(327.4)										
Picudo		0.672b	0.014a	5.337b	3.355a	0.575a	0.656a	13.3	27.44a	0.027b	0.932
Hojiblanca		0.949a	0.017a	21.09a	4.149a	0.629a	0.704a	1.1	28.70a	0.054a	0.953
Picual		-	-	-	-	-	0.024b	0.2	0.310b	0.058a	0.862
2007/2008	(243.8)										
Picudo		-	-	-	-	-	0.003ab	0.4	0.074ab	0.006c	0.882
Hojiblanca		0.697	0.007	68.942	1.758	0.106	0.124a	2.5	1.025a	0.020b	0.907
Picual		-	-	-	-	-	0b	0.0	0b	0.046a	0.842

^aEach value is the mean of data from six olive trees. For each column, means with the same letter are not significantly different according to the least significant differences (LSD) test at $P = 0.05$ or the nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis test at $P = 0.05$ depending on normality and homogeneity of variances of data.

^bNonlinear fit of disease progress curve using the Weibull model [$Y = A(1 - \exp\{-[B(t - C)]^D\})$ equation 3], where A = upper asymptote parameter, B = intrinsic rate of Y increase over time, C = length of delay before the onset the epidemic, D = location of inflection point, Y = the final incidence index of the model, and t = time of disease assessment in days.

^cTotal rainfall of September, October, and November

^dPercentage of fruit with latent infection at the onset of the epidemic in early November.

^eArea under disease progress curve estimated by trapezoidal integration.

^fSlope of regressions for fruit ripening from 0 (green) to 4 (black) over time [fruit ripening class (0–4) = $a + b \times t$ (t = time in days)] and its determination coefficient (R^2).

LEGEND TO THE FIGURES

Figure 1. Effect of cultivar on conidial production by *Colletotrichum acutatum* on “soapy” olive fruit. **A**, Number of conidia produced per soapy fruit. **B**, Number of conidia produced per unit of surface area (mm^2) of soapy fruit. Bars represent the standard error of the mean. Columns with the same letters are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$) according to the Kruskal-Wallis test.

Figure 2. Effect of temperature on the number of *Colletotrichum acutatum* conidia produced per unit surface area of mummified olive fruit cv. Hojiblanca. Points are the means of 60 replicate mummies, and bars represent the standard error of the mean. The line shows the fit of Yin’s nonlinear model to the experimental data.

Figure 3. Effect of wetness duration (h) on the number of *Colletotrichum acutatum* conidia produced per unit surface area of mummified olive fruit cv. Hojiblanca. Points are the means of 60 replicate mummies, and bars represent the standard error of the mean. The line shows the fit of Yin’s nonlinear model to the experimental data.

Figure 4. Effect of repeated incubation followed by washing of mummified olive fruit cv. Hojiblanca infected by *Colletotrichum acutatum* on the cumulative number of conidia produced per unit surface area of mummy. The fruit were incubated and washed from one to 14 times; washing simulated removal of conidia by rain. Points are the means of 100 replicate mummies, and bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 5. Conidial production by *Colletotrichum acutatum* (per mm^2 of affected fruit) on mummified fruit that were placed in the tree canopy (= aerial mummies), on the soil surface, or in the soil (5 cm depth) from May to October in 2006 and 2008. Points are the mean of 50 replicate mummies, and bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 6. Progress curves of anthracnose disease caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* in olive cvs. Hojiblanca (susceptible), Picudo (susceptible), and Picual (resistant) under field conditions in two seasons (2005-2006 and 2006-2007). In the upper graph, each kind of symbol represents an individual olive tree, and each point is the mean proportion (from 0 to 1, i.e., from no fruit with anthracnose to all fruit with anthracnose) calculated with data from four cardinal positions with ~100 fruit per position. Solid lines represent the predicted disease progress curves calculated by the Weibull function. In the middle graph, each point is the mean proportion of latent infection based on 1000–1500 fruit per cultivar. In the lower graph, each point represents the mean number of symptomatic or non-symptomatic fallen fruit per unit area of soil surface as calculated with data from six trees per cultivar.

Figure 7. Relationship between the fruit ripening rate in olive trees of cvs. Picudo, Hojiblanca, and Picual and final incidence of anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7